

DELIVERABLE D8.7

Project website and social media

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Work Package No - Title	WP8 Communication, dissemination, outreach activities
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Date released by WP leader	
Date released by Coordinator	

Dissemination Level	(X)
PU: Public	X
CO: Confidential, only for members for the consortium	

Deliverable type	(X)
R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DIS: Websites, patents, filing, press and media actions, videos, etc	
OTHER: Software, technical diagram	X
ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot	

Revision			
Version	Date	Changed	Comments
1	20/09/2021		INITIAL VERSION

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1 INTRODUCTION AND SUMMARY

1.1 Purpose of the document

A project website will be developed and also continuously updated with project progress information. It will include the dissemination activity from the partners.

It can be found here: icarus.eu.com

ICARUS can also be found on LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/icarus-easme>

2 WEBSITE

This tool will help the partners to disseminate about the project aim, their participation to events and the main public results generated. It will provide access to the consortium, the people and research teams involved and their specific expertise (in a section dedicated to the consortium).

The website will be regularly updated. Of course, the consent of all partners for proper will be necessary for good IPR management, following the rules described in the Consortium Agreement. The structure of the website is currently composed of 5 sections which are listed and described below with some screen copies to illustrate.

1. The homepage is presented below:

2. In a nutshell

Section dedicated to the global overview of the project and the main technological bottlenecks in the field, new alternatives to be developed notably through ICARUS.

TODAY'S CHALLENGE

A common feature of photovoltaics, microelectronics and sensors is their outstanding growth perspective, Europe having strong ambitions for them, and they all rely on a critical upstream process: the transformation of silicon metal (a critical raw material) into wafers.

All the downstream value chains depend on this CRM. Taking the PV industry as an example, each € created in the upstream industry creates 2.7€ in the downstream value chains. It is of utmost importance to make this upstream value chain safe and efficient. The process turning Si into wafers is very energy intensive (about 80 MWh/t) and generates large waste streams. Upstream processing of silicon to wafers supports several important European industries that currently rely so far mostly on Asian supply, which is a major risk largely understood these last months with the current COVID-19 pandemics.

ICARUS will secure this process to foster European growth on downstream value chains. This will be done by turning the upstream process wastes, rich in highly pure Si and energy-dense, into a secondary raw material.

3. Consortium

The consortium can be discovered through a map of the EU. Every partner is detailed and the people working on the project are presented. This section will be amended through the project life.

4. News & events

This section gathers all the news related to the project; new publications, articles, consortium participation to events...

[In a nutshell](#)
[Consortium](#)
[News & Events](#)
[Library](#)

NEWS & EVENTS

HOME / NEWS & EVENTS

TECHNOLOGIES AND INNOVATIONS

28 AVRIL 2021
Hello world!
[Read More](#)

CONFERENCES AND INDUSTRIAL FAIRS

30 AVRIL 2021
Lorem ipsum dolor
[Read More](#)

POLICIES AND REGULATIONS

30 AVRIL 2021
elit quisque varius
[Read More](#)

5. Library

Here the documents related to the project activity (papers, public deliverables...) will be made available to the public.

6. Contact

This last section allows to contact directly the consortium / coordinator.

[In a nutshell](#)
[Consortium](#)
[News & Events](#)
[Library](#)
[Contact](#)

CONTACT

HOME / CONTACT

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Share your questions with us!

First name (required)

Last name (required)

Your organization

Country

The footnote contents the EU acknowledgment, to remind that this project was made possible thanks the European grant.

2 LINKEDIN PAGE

ICARUS can also be found on LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/icarus-easme/?viewAsMember=true>

It will share information from the website and from the consortium.

PROCESSING AND REFINING OF SECONDARY RAW MATERIALS

ICARUS EASME
Processing and refining of secondary raw materials
Industrie composants électriques/électroniques · Trondheim

+ Suivre Voir le site web Plus

Accueil Infos Posts Offres d'emploi Personnes

Infos

ICARUS is a European project, which will secure this process to foster European growth on downstream value chains. This will be done by turning the upstream process wastes, rich in highly pure Si and energy-dense, into a secondary raw material.

voir plus

Voir tous les détails

3 CONTENT AND UPDATES

As stated in the Description of Action, all partners are committed to write blogs for these tools, in order to generate a regular stream of new input

Every partner commits to writing (at least) 5 posts in the duration of the project.

The project website will be maintained for a maximum of 3 years after the project end, with an option to transfer the domain to the Exploitation Manager or project coordinator if desired.

